

Corotational stiffness matrices for 2D truss elements

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Abstract: In this work, the tangent stiffness matrix for the geometrically nonlinear analysis of a two-dimensional truss element subjected to large displacements and rotations, and potentially large deformations, is derived based on the Corotational formulation. The tangent matrix is deduced following two equivalent approaches: variational and energy-based. The resulting tangent stiffness matrix of the element makes up the global stiffness matrix of the structure, which is used in incremental and/or iterative numerical methods to capture the geometric nonlinear response.

Keywords: Structural analysis; Geometric nonlinearity; Corotational; Truss model; Bar element;

1. Introduction

A 2D truss element is a 2-noded plane bar with two degrees-of-freedom per node: translations in the directions of orthogonal axes X and Y, which may be referred to global or local coordinate system. The only type of internal force in a truss element is the axial force, produced by normal stresses in the element cross-sections. There is no bending and the element is always straight.

The Corotational formulation establishes a tangent relation between nodal displacements and forces (i.e. a relation between the variation of these quantities or, equivalently, the derivative of internal forces with respect to displacements) by separating rigid-body motions from strain-producing motions. The rigid-body motions are the element translation and rotation, which do not generate internal forces and are measured with respect to the initial configuration using the global coordinate system. The only strain-producing motion of a truss element is its elongation, which generates an internal axial force and is measured with respect to a corotated configuration that translates and rotates with the element so that it eliminates all rigid-body motions. The corotated configuration defines the so-called natural system, which is not exactly a coordinate system, but the set of local displacement and force components that are related to element deformations, called natural displacements and forces (only one component in the case of a truss element).

An important characteristic of the Corotational formulation is that the natural displacements may be considered very small and, therefore, the element can be formulated as linear (infinitesimal strains) in the natural system, with the geometric nonlinearity being introduced in the transformation between the reference systems (natural and global systems). Such characteristic allows the formulation to cope very well with analyses of arbitrarily large rigid motions, but small deformations. However, a truss element may be subjected to a large axial deformation and it requires that nonlinear strain measurements be used. This consideration is left for the last section.

This work is based on the theory presented in [1–8], which has been extensively used in programs developed by the author's research group [9–20].

2. Reference Systems

The displacement and force components of the element may be referred to two systems: the global system of coordinates or the natural system of deformations.

Figure 1.a shows a truss element in the plane defined by global axes XY . In the initial configuration, the length of the element is L_0 , the angle with the horizontal axis is β_0 , and the nodal coordinates are (x_1, y_1) for the first node and (x_2, y_2) for the second node. As the structure is loaded, the element moves from its original configuration to a deformed configuration, in which it assumes a length L and an angle β with the horizontal axis. This movement is defined by node displacements in the global axes directions, which are grouped in vector $\{d_g\}$ of Eq. (1). These displacements are responsible for a translation, a rotation α (given by $\beta - \beta_0$), and an elongation u_n of the element. The first two are rigid-body motions that do not produce strains and stresses in the element. The elongation, given by the difference of lengths shown in Eq. (2), is the movement component that generates internal forces (in this case, axial force), being the only displacement component of the natural system of the truss element.

Figure 1.b shows the positive directions of the resulting nodal forces in the global system, which are grouped in vector $\{f_g\}$ of Eq. (3), and the only force component of the natural system: the axial force P that corresponds to the element elongation. The figure shows the positive direction of the natural internal force, which is a tensile force.

Figure 1 – Components in the global and natural systems of (a) displacements and (b) forces.

$$\{d_g\} = \{d_{x1} \quad d_{y1} \quad d_{x2} \quad d_{y2}\}^T \quad (1)$$

$$u_n = L - L_0 \quad (2)$$

$$\{f_g\} = \{f_{x1} \quad f_{y1} \quad f_{x2} \quad f_{y2}\}^T \quad (3)$$

3. Variational Approach

Using the displacements and forces in both reference systems, the tangent stiffness matrix of the element will be derived. The tangent matrix relates nodal displacements and forces in global system. In fact, due to the nonlinearity, the tangent matrix relates displacement increments to force increments, hence the term “tangent”. In other words, it involves the variation of these quantities. The relation between the variations of global displacements and global forces is obtained from the relation between the variations of other global and natural quantities, as indicated in Fig. 2. The next sections will develop the variational relations of the constitutive law (1), kinematic (2), and equilibrium (3) between the reference systems for obtaining the tangent stiffness matrix in the global system (indicated by $[K_t]$ in Fig. 2).

Figure 2 – Relations between variations of global and natural quantities.

3.1 Displacements and Forces in Natural System (Constitutive Relation)

It was commented that the natural displacements might be considered very small, so engineering (infinitesimal) strains can be used in the natural system (it is also known that engineering strains are problematic in the presence of rigid-body rotation, which is not the case of the natural system). Assuming, also, linear-elastic material behavior and considering the cross-section area to be constant (typical consideration for small strain problems), the axial force is related to the element elongation as follows, where E is the elasticity modulus of the material and A is the element cross-sections area:

$$P = \frac{EA}{L_0} u_n \quad (4)$$

Since only geometric nonlinearity is considered (physical linearity is preserved), the variations of these quantities are similarly related:

$$\delta P = \frac{EA}{L_0} \delta u_n \quad (5)$$

3.2 Displacements in Natural and Global Systems (Kinematic Relation)

To find a relation between displacements in natural and global systems, consider a small movement (variation) from the deformed configuration, as shown in Fig. 3. In that figure δd is the vector of net variations (difference of global displacements variations of second and first node). In the deformed configuration, the unit vector in element axial direction is e_1 , and e_2 is the unit vector perpendicular to e_1 (so that the result is a right-handed orthogonal coordinate system). The variations of element elongation, δu_n , and rigid-body rotation, $\delta\alpha$, are also indicated.

Figure 3 – Small movement (variation) from the deformed configuration.

The components in global system of the vector of net variations and the local unit vectors are:

$$\{\delta d\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \delta d_{x2} - \delta d_{x1} \\ \delta d_{y2} - \delta d_{y1} \end{Bmatrix} \quad \{e_1\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \cos \beta \\ \sin \beta \end{Bmatrix} \quad \{e_2\} = \begin{Bmatrix} -\sin \beta \\ \cos \beta \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

For an infinitesimal angle change, the variation of element elongation is obtained by the scalar product between the unit axial vector of deformed configuration and the net variations vector, as in Eq. (7), which gives the component of δd projected along the direction of e_1 (proof in appendix C). Furthermore, still because of an infinitesimal angle change, the variation of rigid-body rotation can be approximated by the arc-length expressed in Eq. (8).

$$\delta u_n = \{e_1\}^T \{\delta d\} \quad (7)$$

$$L \cdot \delta\alpha = \{e_2\}^T \{\delta d\} \quad (8)$$

By multiplying these vectors and organizing the terms, the variations of element elongation and rigid-body rotation can be related to the variation of nodal displacements in global system as shown in Eq. (9) and Eq. (10), where vectors $\{r\}$ and $\{z\}$ are defined.

$$\delta u_n = \begin{Bmatrix} -\cos \beta & -\sin \beta & \cos \beta & \sin \beta \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta d_{x1} \\ \delta d_{y1} \\ \delta d_{x2} \\ \delta d_{y2} \end{Bmatrix} = \{r\}^T \{\delta d_g\} \quad (9)$$

$$\delta \alpha = \frac{1}{L} \begin{Bmatrix} \sin \beta & -\cos \beta & -\sin \beta & \cos \beta \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta d_{x1} \\ \delta d_{y1} \\ \delta d_{x2} \\ \delta d_{y2} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{L} \{z\}^T \{\delta d_g\} \quad (10)$$

3.3 Forces in Natural and Global Systems (Equilibrium Relation)

Figure 4 shows the positive directions of the components of nodal forces in the local system of the element (identified by apostrophes, to differentiate from the components of the global system), and the force component of the natural system (the axial force P). It is easy to establish a relation between the forces of these two systems, which is given by Eq. (11) and written in compact form in Eq. (12), where vector $\{S\}$ is identified.

Figure 4 – Force components in natural and local systems.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} f'_{x1} \\ f'_{y1} \\ f'_{x2} \\ f'_{y2} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} -1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} P \quad (11)$$

$$\{f_l\} = \{S\} P \quad (12)$$

The relation between nodal forces in local and global systems is also trivial to establish. By an equilibrium inspection of the force components in Figures 1.b and 4, it is possible to relate them as in Eq. (13), or in compact form in Eq. (14), where the rotation matrix $[R]$ is identified.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} f_{x1} \\ f_{y1} \\ f_{x2} \\ f_{y2} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \beta & -\sin \beta & 0 & 0 \\ \sin \beta & \cos \beta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cos \beta & -\sin \beta \\ 0 & 0 & \sin \beta & \cos \beta \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} f'_{x1} \\ f'_{y1} \\ f'_{x2} \\ f'_{y2} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

$$\{f_g\} = [R]\{f_l\} \quad (14)$$

Using Equations (12) and (14), we can now determine the relation between force components in global and natural systems as follows. Note that the product of rotation matrix $[R]$ by vector $\{S\}$, that relates forces of local and natural systems, results in the same vector $\{r\}$, defined in Eq. (9) to relate the variations of element elongation and global displacements (see the reason in Appendix B):

$$\{f_g\} = [R]\{S\}P \quad (15)$$

$$\{f_g\} = \{r\}P \quad (16)$$

Once the relation between global and natural forces is known, the variation of these quantities, in which we are interested, is obtained by the product rule:

$$\{\delta f_g\} = \{r\} \delta P + \{\delta r\} P \quad (17)$$

In this expression, it is necessary to determine the variation of vector $\{r\}$. Using the chain rule, we get to Eq. (19), where vector $\{z\}$ is identified. It should be observed that $\delta\beta = \delta\alpha$ (in fact, $\delta\beta = \delta\beta_0 + \delta\alpha$ and $\delta\beta_0 = 0$), so Eq. (10) is used to replace the variation of the element angle in Eq. (20), resulting in Eq. (21).

$$\{\delta r\} = \delta \{-\cos \beta \quad -\sin \beta \quad \cos \beta \quad \sin \beta\}^T \quad (18)$$

$$\{\delta r\} = \{\sin \beta \quad -\cos \beta \quad -\sin \beta \quad \cos \beta\}^T \delta\beta \quad (19)$$

$$\{\delta r\} = \{z\} \delta\beta \quad (20)$$

$$\{\delta r\} = \frac{1}{L} \{z\} \{z\}^T \{\delta d_g\} \quad (21)$$

3.4 Tangent Stiffness Matrix

All the necessary relations between global and natural quantities have been established in the previous sections in order to develop a variationally consistent tangent stiffness matrix in the global system. These relations are illustrated in Fig. 5, where the bold equation indicates the unknown relation that is being sought. This unknown relation is provided by the tangent matrix, which is also defined as the differentiation of internal global forces with respect to global displacements (tangent to the curve of nodal displacements versus nodal forces).

Figure 5 – Established relations between the variations of global and natural quantities.

Equation (17), at the bottom of Fig. 5, is written as Eq. (22) by using Eq. (21) to express the variation of vector $\{r\}$. Equation (5), on the right side of Fig. 5, is then applied to express the variation of natural force in terms of the variation of natural displacement, resulting in Eq. (23). Finally, Eq. (9), at the top of Fig. 5, is used to replace the variation of natural displacement in terms of the variation of global displacements, resulting in Eq. (24).

$$\{\delta f_g\} = \{r\} \delta P + \frac{P}{L} \{z\} \{z\}^T \{\delta d_g\} \quad (22)$$

$$\{\delta f_g\} = \{r\} \frac{EA}{L_0} \delta u_n + \frac{P}{L} \{z\} \{z\}^T \{\delta d_g\} \quad (23)$$

$$\{\delta f_g\} = \frac{EA}{L_0} \{r\} \{r\}^T \{\delta d_g\} + \frac{P}{L} \{z\} \{z\}^T \{\delta d_g\} \quad (24)$$

Observing that $\{\delta d_g\}$ is a common factor on the right hand side of Eq. (24), the relation between variations of global forces and global displacements is finally achieved in Eq. (25). This expression provides the tangent stiffness matrix of a 2D truss element referred to the global system. It can be observed that the tangent matrix is generated by the sum of two stiffness components: an elastic stiffness matrix $[K_e]$, which depends only on element properties, and a geometric stiffness matrix $[K_g]$, which depends on the internal axial force.

$$\{\delta f_g\} = \left(\frac{EA}{L_0} \{r\} \{r\}^T + \frac{P}{L} \{z\} \{z\}^T \right) \{\delta d_g\} \quad (25)$$

$$\{\delta f_g\} = ([K_e] + [K_g]) \{\delta d_g\} \quad (26)$$

$$\{\delta f_g\} = [K_t] \{\delta d_g\} \quad (27)$$

If we develop the expressions of the elastic and geometric matrices, we obtain the results below for these matrices in the global axes system, where c and s stand for $\cos(\beta)$ and $\sin(\beta)$, respectively:

$$[K_e] = \frac{EA}{L_0} \begin{bmatrix} c^2 & cs & -c^2 & -cs \\ cs & s^2 & -cs & -s^2 \\ -c^2 & -cs & c^2 & cs \\ -cs & -s^2 & cs & s^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad [K_g] = \frac{P}{L} \begin{bmatrix} s^2 & -cs & -s^2 & cs \\ -cs & c^2 & cs & -c^2 \\ -s^2 & cs & s^2 & -cs \\ cs & -c^2 & -cs & c^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

Considering an element with its local axes aligned with the global axes (i.e. assuming $\beta = 0$), we can check the results for the elastic and geometric matrices referred to the local system of the element:

$$[K_e] = \frac{EA}{L_0} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad [K_g] = \frac{P}{L} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

Remember that the assumption for formulating the element in the natural system was that deformations are very small, so engineering strain was used. As a result, the geometric stiffness matrix does not contribute with axial rigidity by increasing or decreasing the element stiffness in a pure axial motion. The main effect of the geometric stiffness is on the rotational rigid-body motion of the element.

It is also interesting to observe that it would not be possible to derive the geometric matrix directly in the local system, since it comes from the variation of vector $\{r\}$ – second term of Eq. (17) – that only exists because this vector is a function of the rotation angle, so the product rule is applied to obtain Eq. (17) from Eq. (16). If the local X-axis of the element coincides with global X-axis, then vector $\{r\}$ would be simply $\{-1, 0, 1, 0\}^T$. The reason for this is that the local and natural systems are aligned, so a transformation between these systems would not cause the internal force to change direction, which is the effect captured by the geometric stiffness.

4. Energy-Based Approach

The tangent stiffness matrix of the 2D truss element could be derived by directly applying constitutive, kinematic and equilibrium relations between the two reference systems because of the simplicity of this element. A more general approach for dealing with complex finite elements is based on energy principles. For the truss element studied here, the potential energy is:

$$U = \frac{1}{2} P u_n \quad (30)$$

4.1 Internal Forces Vector

The first derivative of the potential energy with respect to the vector of global nodal displacements gives us the internal force vector in the global system:

$$\{f_g\} = \frac{\partial U}{\partial \{d_g\}} \quad (31)$$

Using the product rule to derive the potential energy, we obtain:

$$\{f_g\} = \frac{1}{2} \left(P \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} + u_n \frac{\partial P}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right) \quad (32)$$

As explained in section 3.1, engineering strain is used to relate the axial force with the element elongation according to Eq. (4), which leads us to rewrite the previous expression as follows:

$$\{f_g\} = \frac{1}{2} \left(P \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} + u_n \frac{EA}{L_0} \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(P \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} + P \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right) = P \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \quad (33)$$

It is necessary to calculate the derivatives of the natural displacement (element elongation) with respect to each component of global displacements. To do so, we express the elongation as the difference of deformed and initial lengths and note that the derivatives of the initial length with respect to global displacements are null, leaving only the deformed length, which is written in terms of initial node coordinates and global displacements in Eq. (35).

$$\frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \frac{\partial (L - L_0)}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \{d_g\}} \quad (34)$$

$$L = \sqrt{((x_2 + dx_2) - (x_1 + dx_1))^2 + ((y_2 + dy_2) - (y_1 + dy_1))^2} \quad (35)$$

Therefore, the derivative of element elongation with respect to the vector of global displacements is given in Eq. (36), and the vector of internal nodal forces in global system is given in Eq. (37), which is the same result previously obtained in Eq. (16).

$$\frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \left\{ \frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{x1}} \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{y1}} \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{x2}} \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{y2}} \right\}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} -\cos \beta \\ -\sin \beta \\ \cos \beta \\ \sin \beta \end{Bmatrix} \quad (36)$$

$$\{f_g\} = P \begin{Bmatrix} -\cos \beta \\ -\sin \beta \\ \cos \beta \\ \sin \beta \end{Bmatrix} \quad (37)$$

4.2 Tangent Stiffness Matrix

The tangent stiffness is found by taking the second derivative of the potential energy with respect to the global displacements vector:

$$[K_t] = \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \quad (38)$$

This is the same of taking the first derivative of the vector of internal forces with respect to the global displacements vector. Writing the vector of internal forces as in Eq. (33), we get:

$$[K_t] = \frac{\partial \{f_g\}}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \{d_g\}} \left(P \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \{d_g\}} \left(\frac{EA}{L_0} u_n \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right) \quad (39)$$

Using the product rule results in the expression of the tangent stiffness matrix of the truss element, which is composed of the elastic stiffness and the geometric stiffness:

$$[K_t] = \frac{EA}{L_0} \left\{ \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\} \left\{ \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\}^T + \frac{EA}{L_0} u_n \left[\frac{\partial^2 u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \right] \quad (40)$$

The elastic stiffness matrix is obtained from the first term of Eq. (40), the one that depend on the first derivatives of element elongation with respect to the vector of global displacements. Using the derivative results, given in Eq. (36), we arrive at the elastic stiffness matrix in global system, the same of Eq. (28), where c and s stand for $\cos(\beta)$ and $\sin(\beta)$, respectively:

$$[K_e] = \frac{EA}{L_0} \left\{ \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\} \left\{ \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\}^T = \frac{EA}{L_0} \begin{Bmatrix} -c \\ -s \\ c \\ s \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} -c & -s & c & s \end{Bmatrix} \quad (41)$$

$$[K_e] = \frac{EA}{L_0} \begin{bmatrix} c^2 & cs & -c^2 & -cs \\ cs & s^2 & -cs & -s^2 \\ -c^2 & -cs & c^2 & cs \\ -cs & -s^2 & cs & s^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (42)$$

The geometric stiffness matrix is obtained from the second term of Eq. (40). To evaluate that term, it is necessary to determine the second derivative of the element elongation with respect to the global displacements vector.

$$[K_g] = P \frac{\partial^2 u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \quad (43)$$

From Eq. (34), we recall that taking the derivative of the element elongation with respect to the global displacements vector is the same as taking the derivative of the deformed length:

$$\frac{\partial^2 u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} = \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x1}^2} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x1} \partial d_{y1}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x1} \partial d_{x2}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x1} \partial d_{y2}} \\ & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y1}^2} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y1} \partial d_{x2}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y1} \partial d_{y2}} \\ & & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x2}^2} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x2} \partial d_{y2}} \\ & \text{sym} & & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y2}^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (44)$$

Then, based on the expression of the deformed length of Eq. (35), the results of the second derivatives of the element elongation with respect to each component of the vector of global displacements are:

$$\frac{\partial^2 u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} = \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} = \frac{1}{L} \begin{bmatrix} s^2 & -cs & -s^2 & cs \\ -cs & c^2 & cs & -c^2 \\ -s^2 & cs & s^2 & -cs \\ cs & -c^2 & -cs & c^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (45)$$

The geometric stiffness matrix in global system is the same of that obtained in Eq. (28):

$$[K_g] = \frac{P}{L} \begin{bmatrix} s^2 & -cs & -s^2 & cs \\ -cs & c^2 & cs & -c^2 \\ -s^2 & cs & s^2 & -cs \\ cs & -c^2 & -cs & c^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (46)$$

5. Large Deformations

In some cases, the truss elements may be subjected to a very large axial deformation, of compression or traction. In these cases, the assumption that the element elongation is small is no longer valid and engineering strain cannot be used in the natural system to compute the axial force. A nonlinear strain measurement is required, and the Green-Lagrange strain will be employed.

First, the axial displacement field of the element is taken as a linear interpolation of the element elongation:

$$u(x) = \frac{x}{L_0} u_n \quad (47)$$

Figure 6 – Axial displacement field.

The definitions of the axial component of the engineering strain tensor, ε_e , and Green-Lagrange strain tensor, ε_{GL} , are:

$$\varepsilon_e = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \quad \varepsilon_{GL} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right)^2 \quad (48)$$

Based on the linear interpolation of the displacement field, we can express the strains in terms of the element elongation and initial length:

$$\varepsilon_e = \frac{u_n}{L_0} \quad \varepsilon_{GL} = \frac{u_n}{L_0} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{u_n^2}{L_0^2} \quad (49)$$

Figure 7 shows a comparison between the two strain measurements. It can be observed that the Green-Lagrange tensor provides smaller strain values in compression and larger values in traction.

Figure 7 – Comparison between engineering and Green-Lagrange strains.

When using the Green-Lagrange strain tensor, the resulting stress tensor from the Hooke's law is the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress, σ_{PK2} , which is the energetic conjugate of the Green-Lagrange strain:

$$\sigma_{PK2} = E\varepsilon_{GL} \quad (50)$$

However, the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress has little physical meaning and is not the stress that we are seeking. The engineering stress, σ_e , which is the ratio of the force over the initial area, will be used to compute the axial force considering the initial, undeformed, cross-section area of the element. The relation between the engineering stress and the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress for an incompressible material is:

$$\sigma_e = \sigma_{PK2}(1 + \varepsilon_L) = E\varepsilon_{GL}(1 + \varepsilon_L) \quad (51)$$

Using Eq. (49), the engineering stress resulting from the use of the Green-Lagrange strain can be expressed in terms of the element elongation and initial length as follows:

$$\sigma_e = \frac{E}{L_0} \left(u_n + \frac{3u_n^2}{2L_0^2} + \frac{u_n^3}{2L_0^3} \right) \quad (52)$$

The axial force is obtained from the product of the initial cross-section area by the engineering stress, which gives us the expression for computing the internal axial force considering large deformations:

$$P = A\sigma_e = \frac{EA}{L_0} \left(u_n + \frac{3u_n^2}{2L_0^2} + \frac{u_n^3}{2L_0^3} \right) \quad (53)$$

The derivative of the internal axial force with respect to the element elongation gives the axial stiffness component of the elastic matrix:

$$k = \frac{\partial P}{\partial u_n} = \frac{EA}{L_0} \left(1 + \frac{3u_n}{L_0} + \frac{3u_n^2}{2L_0^2} \right) \quad (54)$$

Note that the axial coefficients of the elastic stiffness matrix have some additional terms to change the stiffness of the element when it is subjected to an axial deformation. In fact, these terms are the result of a local nonlinearity considered in the natural system (the use of finite strains). The geometric stiffness matrix remains the same of the previous sections, since it is only responsible for the effect of rotating the internal force. Equations (55) and (56) shows the stiffness matrices in the local coordinate system of the element.

$$[K_e] = \frac{EA}{L_0} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{EA}{L_0} \frac{3u_n}{L_0} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{EA}{L_0} \frac{3u_n^2}{2L_0^2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (55)$$

$$[K_g] = \frac{P}{L} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (56)$$

To show the effect of considering the large deformation formulation, Fig. 8 provides the results of the nonlinear analysis of a truss element subjected to a tensile force. The blue line is the result of the end node displacement when engineering strain is used to compute the internal axial force and the tangent stiffness matrix based on this assumption is employed. The result is the same of a linear analysis. When the formulation based on the Green-Lagrange strain is used, the displacements are smaller, as indicated by the orange line. This is because, according to Fig. 7, the Green Lagrange strain gives larger values than engineering strain when the element stretches, so larger values of internal force is also obtained in each step of the analysis.

Figure 8 – Comparison between small strain analysis with finite strain analysis.

Although the material behavior is still considered linear-elastic during this large deformation formulation, this is not usually the case. Large deformations are generally related to physical nonlinearity.

Appendix A – Geometric Matrix for Large Deformations

In section 5, the effect of considering a large deformation was the inclusion of additional terms to the axial coefficients of the elastic matrix, so that the stiffness of the element is changed when it is stretched or compressed. This additional axial stiffness can also be considered in the geometric matrix, leading to a very commonly used version of the geometric stiffness matrix that will be presented.

To include the additional axial stiffness terms to the geometric matrix, it is necessary to consider the element length as constant when deriving the tangent stiffness matrix. The effect of this consideration is a compensating axial stiffness to capture the nonlinear force-displacement relation during deformation.

In the energy-based approach, it means to take the length of the element as a constant during the second derivatives of element elongation in Eq. (44). For example, considering the element length given in Eq. (35), the first derivative of the element elongation with respect to the global displacement d_{x1} is:

$$\frac{\partial u_n}{\partial d_{x1}} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{x1}} = -\frac{(x_2 + dx_2) - (x_1 + dx_1)}{\sqrt{((x_2 + dx_2) - (x_1 + dx_1))^2 + ((y_2 + dy_2) - (y_1 + dy_1))^2}} \quad (\text{A1})$$

$$\frac{\partial u_n}{\partial d_{x1}} = -\frac{(x_2 + dx_2) - (x_1 + dx_1)}{L} = -\cos \beta \quad (\text{A2})$$

If the denominator of Eq. (A2) is considered a constant, the second derivative of the element elongation with respect to the global displacement component is:

$$\frac{\partial^2 u_n}{\partial d_{x1}^2} = \frac{1}{L} \quad (\text{A3})$$

By performing all other derivatives of Eq. (44) in the same way, we get the geometric stiffness matrix of Eq. (A4). This matrix is similar to the geometric matrix previously obtained, but it has stiffness coefficients in the axial positions to contribute with the gain or loss of stiffness during deformation. Furthermore, it is interesting to note that this matrix is invariant with respect to rotations and is, therefore, identical in the local and global coordinate systems.

$$[K_g] = \frac{P}{L} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A4})$$

In the variational approach, this is equivalent to consider a constant element length when computing the variation of vector $\{r\}$ in Eq. (18). To do so, the variations of the cosine and sine of the element angle must be based on a constant length, which is done in the sequence.

As in section 3.2, consider a small movement (variation) from the deformed configuration, as shown in Fig. A1. This figure is an adaptation of Fig. 3, but indicating that the angle with horizontal axis of the configuration after variation is β' .

Figure A1 – Small movement (variation) from the deformed configuration

Considering that the element length in both configurations (before and after variation) is the same, the cosine and sine of the element angle in both configurations can be expressed as:

$$\cos \beta = \frac{(x_2 + dx_2) - (x_1 + dx_1)}{L} \quad \cos \beta' = \frac{(x_2 + dx_2 + \delta dx_2) - (x_1 + dx_1 + \delta dx_1)}{L} \quad (\text{A5})$$

$$\sin \beta = \frac{(y_2 + dy_2) - (y_1 + dy_1)}{L} \quad \sin \beta' = \frac{(y_2 + dy_2 + \delta dy_2) - (y_1 + dy_1 + \delta dy_1)}{L} \quad (\text{A6})$$

The variation of the cosine and sine of the angle is then the difference between these values:

$$\delta \cos \beta = \cos \beta' - \cos \beta = \frac{\delta dx_2 - \delta dx_1}{L} \quad (\text{A7})$$

$$\delta \sin \beta = \sin \beta' - \sin \beta = \frac{\delta dy_2 - \delta dy_1}{L} \quad (\text{A8})$$

Based on these results, the variation of vector $\{r\}$ is given below, where matrix $[z]$ is defined to write it in a compact form:

$$\{\delta r\} = \frac{1}{L} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta d_{x1} \\ \delta d_{y1} \\ \delta d_{x2} \\ \delta d_{z2} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{L} [z] \{\delta d_g\} \quad (\text{A9})$$

The geometric stiffness matrix is directly obtained from the variation of vector $\{r\}$, and the result is the same of Eq. (A4):

$$[K_g] = \frac{P}{L}[z] = \frac{P}{L} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A10})$$

This version of the geometric stiffness matrix should be used in the Corotational formulation only when large strains are considered to compute the internal axial force, as in Eq. (53). Otherwise, the additional axial stiffness coefficients will be useless to converge to an equilibrium solution that is based on small strains. This is because the solution of a purely axial nonlinear analysis that uses engineering strains is the same of a linear analysis, so the change in axial stiffness, promoted by the additional terms of the geometric matrix, will slow down the convergence process.

It should be mentioned that using this version of the geometric stiffness matrix for performing the nonlinear analysis based on Green-Lagrange strains is not as efficient as using the matrices obtained directly from the derivation of the internal axial force that considers large deformations, which is given Equations (55) and (56).

Appendix B – The Principle of Contragradiency

The vector whose transpose relates the variation of displacements in global and natural systems, in Eq. (9), is the same vector that relates forces in global and natural systems, in Eq. (16). This corresponds to the Principle of Contragradiency of structural analysis.

Therefore, the relation of Eq. (16) could also be derived from the Principle of Virtual Displacements, considering that the work performed by forces going through virtual displacements in the global and natural systems is equal. This is seen in Eq. (B1), where the virtual work must hold for an arbitrary virtual displacement. Writing the natural displacement in terms of global displacements, in Eq. (B2), and canceling it from the both sides of Eq. (B2), we obtain in Eq. (B3) the same relation of Eq. (16).

$$\{\delta d_g\}^T \{f_g\} = \delta u_n \cdot P \quad (\text{B1})$$

$$\{\delta d_g\}^T \{f_g\} = (\{r\}^T \{\delta d_g\})^T P \quad (\text{B2})$$

$$\{f_g\} = \{r\} P \quad (\text{B3})$$

Appendix C – Variation of Element Elongation

Consider an element with initial length L_0 aligned with the horizontal axis, as shown in Fig. C1. After it moves, the length becomes L_1 , the angle of rotation is α , and the displacements of the nodes are d_{x1} , d_{y1} , d_{x2} , d_{y2} . In the figure, the net displacements are applied to the second node.

Figure C1 – Movement in element configuration.

The elongation of the element during the movement is the difference of the initial and final lengths. With some basic algebraic manipulations, the expression of the element elongation can be developed as follows:

$$u_n = L_1 - L_0 \quad (C1)$$

$$u_n = \left((L_0 + dx)^2 + (dy)^2 \right)^{1/2} - L_0 \quad (C2)$$

$$u_n + L_0 = \left((L_0 + dx)^2 + dy^2 \right)^{1/2} \quad (C3)$$

$$(u_n + L_0)^2 = (L_0 + dx)^2 + dy^2 \quad (C4)$$

$$u_n^2 + 2u_n L_0 + L_0^2 = L_0^2 + 2dxL_0 + dx^2 + dy^2 \quad (C5)$$

$$u_n^2 + 2u_n L_0 = 2dxL_0 + d^2 \quad (C6)$$

In this step, we apply the law of cosines to write d^2 as the expression inside the parenthesis of Eq. (C7), and continue to manipulate the expression:

$$u_n^2 + 2u_n L_0 = 2dxL_0 + (L_0^2 + L_1^2 - 2L_0 L_1 \cos \alpha) \quad (C7)$$

$$u_n^2 + 2u_n L_0 = 2dxL_0 + L_0^2 + (L_0 + u_n)^2 - 2L_0 (L_0 + u_n)^2 \cos \alpha \quad (C8)$$

$$u_n^2 + 2u_n L_0 = 2dxL_0 + L_0^2 + L_0^2 + 2u_n L_0 + u_n^2 - 2L_0^2 \cos \alpha - 2u_n L_0 \cos \alpha \quad (C9)$$

Canceling the terms and dividing the whole equation by $2L_0$, we arrive at the expression that provides the element elongation in terms of nodal displacements, initial length, and rotation angle:

$$u_n = \frac{dx + L_0 (1 - \cos \alpha)}{\cos \alpha} \quad (C10)$$

When the rotation angle is very small ($\cos(\alpha) = 1$), we get the following result for the element elongation, which justifies the projection of d in the axial direction to be taken as the variation of the element elongation in Eq. (7). In other words, $\delta u_n = \delta L - \delta L_0 = \delta L$.

$$u_n = dx = dx_2 - dx_1 \quad (\text{C11})$$

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